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FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND *IN VITRO* - *IN VIVO* EVALUATION OF DARUNAVIR SELF EMULSIFYING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM (SEDDS)

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of present work was to prepare a solid SEDDS for enhancement of oral bioavailability of Darunavir, a poorly water soluble drug. The solubility of the drug was determined in various vehicles. A pseudo ternary phase diagram was constructed to identify the self-micro emulsification region. Further, the resultant formulations were investigated for clarity, phase separation, globule size, effect of pH and dilutions and freeze-thaw stability. The optimized SMEDDS (F4) formulation of Darunavir contained Capmul MCM (Oil), Kolliphor HS 15 (Surfactant) and PEG 400 (Co-surfactant). Optimized liquid SEDDS having particle size (71.1nm), zeta potential (-40.6mV), in-vitro dissolution study (96.34%). This optimized formulation was converted in to solid SEDDS by adding required quantity of Neusilin US2 as adsorbing agent used for in vitro dissolution and bioavailability assessment. The oral bioavailability of Darunavir from solid SEDDS was 1.6-fold higher compared to that of Darunavir suspension in rats, suggesting a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in oral bioavailability of Darunavir from solid SEDDS. The present exploratory work successfully illustrates the potential utility of S-SMEDDS formulation for the delivery of poor water-soluble drug Darunavir, which may result in improved therapeutic performance.

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INTRODUCTION

Oral route has been the major route of drug delivery for the chronic treatment of human diseases. However, oral delivery of 50% of the drugs is hampered because of the high lipophilicity [1]. In drug discovery, about 40% of the new drug candidates display low solubility in water, which leads to poor bioavailability, high intra subject/inter subject variability and lack of dose proportionality. Therefore producing suitable formulations is very important to improve the solubility and bioavailability of such drugs [2]. Self-emulsifying systems are a useful means of improving the bioavailability of poorly water soluble drugs, particularly the self-micro emulsifying drug delivery systems are well known for their potential as alternative strategies for delivery of hydrophobic drugs [3].

SEDDS are isotropic mixtures of drug, oil/lipid, surfactant and/or co-surfactant, which form fine emulsion/lipid droplets on dilution with physiological fluid. The researchers now focused on solid SEDDS area were increasing. Solid SEDDS prepared by solidification of liquid or semisolid self emulsifying ingredients into powders, have gained popularity. These solid SEDDS were prepared by extrusion/spheronization method or wet granulation in a high shear mixer and adsorption to solid carriers involves addition of the liquid formulation onto carriers by mixing in a blender. Oral delivery of poorly water-soluble compounds is to pre-dissolve the compound in a suitable solvent and fill the formulation into capsules. The main benefit of this approach is that pre-dissolving the compound overcomes the initial rate limiting step of particulate dissolution in the aqueous environment within the GI tract [4].

Darunavir was a poorly water soluble antiviral drug and inhibitor of the human immuno deficiency virus protease. Darunavir was a second-generation protease inhibitor and it was used to treatment of HIV infection. Darunavir was selectively inhibiting the cleavage of HIV-1 encoded Gag-Pol polyprotein in infected cells, thereby preventing the formation of mature virus particles. Darunavir was co-administered with ritonavir and with other antiretroviral agents, is indicated for the treatment of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV-1) infection [5].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Darunavir was generous gift from Hetero drugs limited, Hyderabad, India. Capmul MCM, Vitamin E TPGS, Capryol 90, Gelucire 44/14 and Castor oil were obtained from Granules India limited, Hyderabad. Lauroglycol, Captex 355 and Labrasol were obtained from Aurobindo Pharma limited, Hyderabad. Kolliphor RH 40 and Kolliphor HS 15 were gifted from BASF, Mumbai. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Methods

Solubility studies

The solubility study was used to find out the suitable oil, surfactant and co-surfactant that possess good solubilizing capacity for Darunavir. The solubility of Darunavir in various oils (Capmul MCM, Capryol 90, Castor oil, Captex 355, Vitamin E TPGS) (shown in table), surfactants (Kolliphor HS 15, Kolliphor RH 40, Gelucire 44/14, labrasol, Lauroglycol) (shown in table 15), and co-surfactants (PEG400, PEG 600, Propylene glycol) (shown in table) were determined by mixing excess amount of Darunavir (approximately 600mg) with 2 ml of each of the individual components. The drug was added to a 5-ml capacity stoppered glass vial and mixed for 10 min with each component using a vortex mixer. The mixture vials were then kept at $37 \pm 1.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ in an isothermal shaker for 72 h until homogeneity. The homogenate samples were then centrifuged at 18,000 rpm for 30 min at 4°C . The supernatant was removed by pipetting and the drug concentration was determined by UV at 262 nm. Concentration of dissolved drug was determined spectrophotometrically [6].

Construction of ternary phase diagram

On the basis of the solubility study of drug, oil, surfactants and co-surfactants were used for construction of phase diagram. Oil, surfactant, and co-surfactant are grouped in three different combinations for phase studies [7]. Surfactant and co-surfactant (Smix) in each group were mixed in different weight ratio (1:1, 1:2, 2:1, 3:1). These Smix ratios are chosen in increasing concentration of surfactant with respect to co-surfactant and in increasing concentration of co surfactant with respect to surfactant for detail study of the phase diagram for formulation of micro emulsion. For each phase diagram, oil, and specific Smix ratio are mixed thoroughly in different weight ratio from 1:9 to 9:1 (1:9, 2:8, 3:7, 4:6, 5:5, 6:4,7:3, 8:2, 9:1) in different glass vials. Different combination of oils and Smix were made so those maximum ratios were covered for the study to delineate the boundaries of phase precisely formed in the phase diagrams. Pseudo-ternary phase diagram was developed using aqueous titration method. Slow titration with aqueous phase is done to each weight ratio of oil and Smix and visual observation is carried out for transparent and easily flow able o/w micro emulsion. The physical state of the micro emulsion was marked on a pseudo-three-component phase diagram with one axis representing oil, the other representing surfactant and the third representing co-surfactant at fixed weight ratios [8].

% Transmittance

The Darunavir SMEDDS were reconstituted with distilled water and the resulting microemulsion was observed visually for any turbidity. Thereafter, its % transmittance was measured at 262 nm using UV spectrophotometer against distilled water as the blank [9].

Emulsification time

A visual test to assess the self-emulsification properties was modified and used in the present study. With the use of this method, a predetermined volume of mixture (0.2 ml) was added to 300 ml of water in a glass beaker under stirring and temperature was maintained at 37°C using a magnetic stirrer. The tendency of formation of emulsion was observed. If the droplet spreads easily in water was judged as 'good' and judged as 'bad' when there was milky or no emulsion or presence of oil droplets [10].

Development of SEDDS Formulations

Weigh accurately 600mg of Darunavir and transferred in to a glass vial. To this Capmul MCM oil was added and warmed on water bath. To this oily mixture, Kolliphor HS 15 (surfactant) and Poly ethylene glycol 400 (Co-surfactant) mixtures was added. Then the components were mixed by gentle stirring and vortex mixing at 37 °C until Darunavir was completely dissolved. Then the mixture was sealed in glass vial and stored at room temperature until used [11]. The composition was given in the Table 1.

Table 1: Formulation Trials of Liquid SEDDS.

Smix (Surfactant: co-urfactant)	Oil: Smix	formulation code	Darunavir (mg)	Oil (capmul mcm) (ml)	Surfactant (kolliphor hs 15) (ml)	Co-surfactant (PEG-400) (ml)
3:1	1:9	F1	300	0.02	0.135	0.045
	1:7	F2	300	0.025	0.131	0.043
	1:6	F3	300	0.028	0.128	0.042
	1:5	F4	300	0.033	0.124	0.041
	1:4	F5	300	0.04	0.12	0.04
	1:9	F6	300	0.02	0.12	0.06
	1:8	F7	300	0.022	0.118	0.059
2:1	1:7	F8	300	0.025	0.116	0.058
	1:6	F9	300	0.028	0.114	0.057

Freeze Thawing

Freeze thawing was employed to evaluate the stability of formulations. The formulations were subjected to 3 to 4 freeze-thaw cycles, which included freezing at -4 °C for 24 hours followed by thawing at 40 °C for 24 hours. Centrifugation was performed at 3000 rpm for 5 minutes. The formulations were then observed for phase separation. Only formulations that were stable to phase separation were selected for further studies [12].

Determination of Drug Content

Accurately measured dose of Darunavir formulation (0.2ml) equivalent to 300mg was taken in volumetric flask and the volume is made to 100ml with phosphate buffer pH 6.8. From this 1ml of solution is taken in a 10ml volumetric flask and is made up to 10ml with buffer. This solution is diluted to 10µg/ml and absorbance was measured at λ_{max} 262 nm against blank. The amount of drug present in 0.2ml of formulation was determined by using UV spectrophotometric method.

$$\% \text{ Drug content} = \frac{\text{Actual amount of drug in SMEDDS}}{\text{Theoretical amount of drug in SMEDDS}} \times 100$$

In Vitro Dissolution Studies of SEDDS

The dissolution test was undertaken with paddle method in 900 ml of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer containing various concentrations of Darunavir at 37 °C with a paddle speed of 50 rpm. The liquid SMEDDS containing 600 mg of Darunavir were filled into hard gelatine capsules (capsule No.00) samples for analysis were collected at appropriate time intervals at 2, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 45, 60min through filters and the concentration of Darunavir was determined in at 262nm by UV [13].

Oil Adsorption Study

The objective of this study was to select adsorbent for preparing free flowing solid Self emulsifying formulation for Darunavir. Microcrystalline cellulose, colloidal silicon dioxide, Neusilin US2, dicalcium phosphate and tricalcium phosphate were used as adsorbents. They were added separately to the optimized liquid S(M)EDDS formulation i.e F4 under stirring (adsorbents were added to 100gms of oil phase until free flowing blend was formed). Neusilin US2 showed higher oil adsorption capacity when compared to microcrystalline cellulose and colloidal silicon dioxide [14].

Conversion of SEDDS to Solid SEDDS

The optimized liquid SEDDS formulation (F4) based on droplet size and dissolution study was converted into free flowing powder by adsorption onto solid carriers. The composition was shown in Table 2. The solid carrier used for adsorption comprised of materials that provided a high surface area with good disintegration characteristics. 200 mg of Neusilin US2 (Magnesium aluminum silicate) was used as a solid carrier. It can adsorb at high levels up to 70% (w/w). The conversion process involved addition of liquid formulation onto carriers under continuous mixing. The powder was dried and filled directly into capsules [15].

Table 2: Composition of Darunavir SEDDS and Solid SEDDS.

S. No	Components (%wt/wt)	F4 Liquid SEDDS (mg)	Solid SEDDS (mg)
1	Darunavir	300	300
2	Capmul MCM	52.78	52.78
3	Kolliphor HS 15	205.00	205
4	PEG-400	71.41	71.41
5	Neusilin US2	-	200

Determination of Drug Content of Solid SEDDS

Accurately weighed dose of Darunavir solid SMEDDS was taken in volumetric flask and dissolved in small quantity of methanol. The volume was made to 100ml with phosphate buffer pH 6.8. From this 1ml of solution was taken in a 10ml volumetric flask and made up to 10ml with buffer. This solution was diluted to 10 μ g/ml and absorbance was measured at λ_{max} 262 nm against blank.

Dissolution Studies of Solid SEDDS

The release of drug from solid SMEDDS formulations and pure drug was determined using a US Pharmacopoeia Type II dissolution apparatus (Here same conditions and media applied as used for SMEDDS. The dissolution media is phosphate buffer pH 6.8 (900ml), and temperature of the dissolution medium was maintained at 37⁰C operated at 50 rpm. A 10ml sample of medium was withdrawn at predetermined intervals 2, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 45 and 60 min and filtered through 0.45- μ m pore size membrane filters. The concentrations were assayed spectrophotometrically at 262nm.

Characterization of SEDDS

Drug-Excipient Compatibility Studies by FTIR

An FTIR-8400S Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan) equipped with attenuated total reflectance (ATR) accessory was used to obtain the infrared spectra of drug in the isotropic mixtures of excipients. Analysis of pure drug i.e., Darunavir, Neusilin US2 and physical mixtures of the drug with the excipients were carried out using diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS)-FTIR with KBr disc. All the samples were dried under vacuum prior to obtaining any spectra in order to remove the influence of residual moisture. For each the spectrum, 8 scans were obtained at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ from a frequency range of 400–4000 cm⁻¹ [16].

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) studies were carried out using DSC 60, having TA60 software, Shimadzu, Japan. Accurately weighed samples were placed on aluminium plate, sealed with aluminium lids and heated at a constant rate of 5⁰C /min, over a temperature range of 0 to 250⁰C [17].

Determination of Droplet Size

The droplet size of the micro emulsions is determined by photon correlation spectroscopy (which analyses the fluctuations in light scattering due to Brownian motion of the particles) using a Zetasizer able to measure sizes between 2 nm and 5000 nm. Light scattering is monitored at 25⁰C at a 90⁰ angle.

Determination of Zeta Potential

The emulsion stability is directly related to the magnitude of the surface charge. The zeta potential of the diluted SEDDS formulation was measured using a zeta meter system. Zeta-potential of the resulting micro emulsion was determined using a Malvern Zetasizer [18].

Micromeritic properties of Solid SEDDS

Prepared S-SEDDS was evaluated for micromeritic properties such as angle of repose, bulk and tapped density, compressibility index and Hausner's ratio [19].

Drug entrapment efficiency of Solid SEDDS

The quantities of the drugs theoretically contained in the SEDDS were compared with the quantity actually obtained, from the drug content studies i.e. the quantity loaded into the SEDDS formulated [20].

Scanning electron microscopy

The surface and shape characteristics of pellets were determined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (HITACHI, S-3700N). Photographs were taken and recorded at suitable magnification [21].

In vivo bioavailability studies

Rats were divided into two groups at random. The rats were fasted for 24 hours prior to the experiments. After 4 hours of dosing, foods were reoffered. First group was administered with pure Darunavir (as such) made suspension with 0.5% methocel and second group was administered solid SMEDDS diluted in 0.5% methocel by oral route at a dose of 300mg/kg. Then, 500 μ L blood samples were collected from the femoral artery at certain times 0.25, 0.50, 1, 1.5, 2, 2, 3, 3.5, 4, 4.5, 6, 8, 12, 16, 18 and 24h post dose and transferred into Eppendorf tubes containing heparin in order to prevent blood clotting. Plasma was separated by centrifugation of the blood at 5000 rpm in cooling centrifuge for 5min to 10 minutes and stored frozen at -20°C until analysis. Samples were analysed with HPLC method was C_{18} (250 \times 4.6 mm i.d) chromatographic column equilibrated with mobile phase buffer and acetonitrile in the proportion of 65:35 (v/v) was used, flow rate was maintained at 1 ml/min and effluents were monitored at 240 nm. The sample was injected using a 20 μ L fixed loop, and the total run time was 10 min. The retention time for Darunavir, cobicistat (internal standard) were detected at retention times of 3.95, 6.75 [22].

Pharmacokinetic analysis

The pharmacokinetic parameters employed to evaluate were maximum plasma concentration (C_{max}), time to attain C_{max} i.e., T_{max} and $t_{1/2}$ values, area under plasma concentration–time curve from zero to the last sampling time (AUC_{0-t}), area under plasma concentration–time curve from zero to infinity ($AUC_{0-\infty}$). AUC_{0-t} was calculated by the linear trapezoidal rule and $AUC_{0-\infty}$ from the following formula.

$$AUC_{0-\infty} = AUC_{0-t} + C_t / K_E$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Solubility studies

The Darunavir pure drug solubility was found to be 34.91 mg/ml. The solubility of the Darunavir drug was tested in different oils phases and maximum solubility was found in Capmul MCM as 50.62 mg/ml (**Figure 1**). The solubility of the drug was tested in different surfactants and co-surfactants, maximum solubility was found in Kolliphor HS-15 as 76.32 mg/ml (**Figure 2**) and 52.26 mg/ml was in PEG-400 respectively (**Figure 3**). Capmul MCS, Kolliphor HS-15 and PEG-400 were used for the formulation of Darunavir SEDDS.

Figure 1: Solubility studies of Darunavir in oils.

Figure 2: Solubility studies of Darunavir in surfactants.

Figure 3: Solubility studies of Darunavir in Co-surfactants.

Construction of ternary phase diagram

From the above chosen oils, surfactants and co-surfactants were taken in different ratios (Table 1) for the construction of ternary phase diagrams to know the emulsion and micro-emulsion domains such that at particular concentration of oil, surfactant and co-solvent ratios, a stable self-emulsifying formulation is formed. The Self emulsification process is affected on the concentration of Kolliphor HS-15 and PEG-400 and their ratio. The phase diagram representing that series I (3:1) and series II (2:1) showed a narrow micro emulsifying domain (Figure 4). So the concentration of oil, surfactant and co-surfactant was selected in these domains for the study. From the phase diagrams, it was observed that self emulsifying region increased with increasing concentrations of surfactant or combination of surfactant and co-surfactant. Efficiency of self-emulsification was good when the surfactant concentration was increased.

Figure 4: Ternary phase diagram of Capmul MCM, Kolliphor HS 15 and PEG 400.

Visual observation and % Transmittance

The clarity of microemulsions was checked by transparency, measured in terms of transmittance (%T). SEDDS forms o/w microemulsion since water is external phase. Some Formulations have % transmittance value greater than 99%. These results indicate the high clarity of microemulsion. In case of other systems %T values were about 97% suggesting less clarity of microemulsions. This may be due to greater particle size of the formulation. Due to higher particle size, oil globules may reduce the transparency of microemulsion and thereby values of % T. The results of %T are as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Visual observation and %Transmittance of different formulations.

Smix (surfactant: Co-surfactant)	Oil: Smix	Visual observation	%Transmittance
3:1	1:9	Transparent	99.56
	1:8	Slightly clear	89.99
	1:7	Transparent	99.50
	1:6	Transparent	92.24
	1:5	Transparent	99.89
	1:4	Transparent	97.12
	1:3	Turbid	70.02
	1:2	Turbid	57.52
	1:1	Turbid	20.99
	6:1	Turbid	18.78
	7:1	Turbid	10.34
	8:1	Turbid	15.89
	9:1	Turbid	45.78
2:1	1:9	Transparent	96.98
	1:8	Transparent	96.22
	1:7	Transparent	97.09
	1:6	Transparent	95.53
	1:5	Slightly clear	87.99
	1:4	Slightly clear	88.84
	1:3	Slightly clear	54.89
	1:2	Slightly clear	48.97
	1:1	Turbid	28.72
	3:1	Turbid	14.99
2:1	Turbid	25.52	

From this liquid mixtures of Capmul MCM, Kolliphor HS 15 and PEG 400 of 1:9, 1:7 1:6 1:5 1:4 oil: Smix ratios belongs to 3:1 Smix and 1:9, 1:8 1:7, 1:6 oil: Smix ratios belongs to 2:1 Smix shown highest % transmittance i.e. above 90%, therefore these ratios are suggested for high clarity of microemulsion. In case of other ratios gave turbid solutions which are not suggesting for microemulsion formulation. The results are tabulated in Table 3.

Emulsification Time

The tendency of formation of emulsion was observed with this method. If the droplet spreads easily in water was judged as 'good' and judged as 'bad' when there was milky or no emulsion or presence of oil droplets. Formulation F4 has % transmittance value greater than 99% (shown in table 3). These results indicate the high clarity of microemulsion. In case of other systems %T values were less than 99% suggesting less clarity of microemulsion. This may be due to greater particle size of the formulation. Due to higher particle size, oil globules may reduce the transparency of microemulsion and thereby values of %T. The results of %T are as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Emulsification time of SEDDS Formulations.

Smix (Surfactant: co-surfactant)	Oil:Smix	Time (min)	Visual observation	Grade
3:1	1:9	<1	Clear fibres, clear solution	A
	1:7	<1	Clear fibres, clear solution	A
	1:6	<1	Very Slight fibres, clear solution	A/B
	1:5	<1	Clear fibres, clear solution	A
	1:4	<1	Slight fibres, clear solution	A/B
	1:9	<1	Very Slight fibres, clear solution	A/B
2:1	1:8	<1	Slight fibres, clear solution	A/B
	1:7	<1	Slight fibres, clear solution	A/B
	1:6	<1	Very Slight fibres, clear solution	A/B

Preparation of Darunavir SEDDS

SEDDS of Darunavir were prepared by using Capmul MCM (Oil), Kolliphor HS 15 (Surfactant) and PEG 400 (Co-surfactant). In the present investigation 9 formulations were prepared and their complete composition is shown in **Table 1**. All the prepared SEDDS were found to be clear.

Freeze thaw method

In thermodynamic stability study, no phase separation and no change of temperature variations on prepared formulations were observed. There was no change in the visual description of samples after centrifugation freeze-thaw cycles.

Drug Content of SEDDS

Actual drug content of all 9 formulations are shown in **Table 5**. The drug content of the prepared SEDDS was found to be in the range of 91.50 – 98.11%. Maximum % drug content i.e. 98.11% was found in the formulation F4.

Table 5: % Assay of different formulations.

Formulation Code	Assay (%)
F1	96.43
F2	96.16
F3	91.50
F4	98.11
F5	94.84
F6	93.76
F7	94.98
F8	92.64
F9	95.31

In Vitro Dissolution Studies of SEDDS

The results of *in vitro* dissolution comparisons of SEDDS formulations are summarized in **Table 6**. The faster and highest drug dissolution from SEDDS may be attributed to the fact that in this formulation, the drug is a solubilized form and upon exposure to dissolution medium results in small droplet that can dissolve rapidly in the dissolution medium. The release from SEDDS formulation F4 was highest (97.34) faster than other SEDDS formulations and pure drug substance indicating influence of droplet size on the rate of drug dissolution.

Table 6: Dissolution profiles of various formulations.

Time (min)	Dissolution media – Phosphate buffer pH 6.8 (% drug release) Formulation Code									
	Pure drug	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	2.29	28.19	14.78	42.01	39.53	25.12	21.76	19.92	29.7	15.33
5	10.10	57.71	66.80	56.75	78.10	46.37	50.18	42.42	42.2	45.96
10	17.90	69.19	74.47	66.62	85.68	52.97	63.91	53.81	63.9	68.05
15	21.12	71.72	79.39	74.63	90.50	61.66	68.52	59.91	71.8	70.76
20	23.41	78.82	82.48	79.92	92.61	75.54	72.39	67.66	79.9	81.82
25	30.70	83.37	87.58	82.79	95.28	80.05	79.86	79.95	81.1	85.27
30	35.81	90.50	91.62	86.34	96.33	87.06	83.84	81.65	84.8	89.07
45	37.19	91.21	91.99	86.88	96.33	87.34	84.31	82.20	85.0	89.43
60	43.60	91.43	92.04	87.11	97.34	87.61	84.56	82.66	85.3	89.71

Selection of optimized formulation

When compared to % transmittance, emulsification test and in vitro drug release studies for all formulations, F4 formulation was found to be best and optimized formulation and further characterized for other studies.

Oil adsorption study

Oil adsorption study was performed for Darunavir by using different adsorbents and results are depicted in Figure 5. Neusilin US2 showed higher oil adsorption capacity when compared to other adsorbents. From oil adsorption study Neusilin US2 was used for the preparation of Solid SEDDS from optimized SEDDS formulation (F4).

Figure 5: Adsorption studies of Darunavir with different adsorbents.

Conversion of SEDDS to Solid SEDDS

On the basis of faster and complete dissolution rate, formulation F4 was selected as optimized formulation and this formulation was converted in to solid SEDDS by adding required quantity of Neusilin US2 as adsorbing agent.

Micromeretic properties of Darunavir solid SEDDS

The micromeretic properties angle of repose, LBD, TBD, Carr's index and Hausner's ratio of the solid SEDDS was found to be 28.31, 0.22, 0.25, 13.30 and 1.16 respectively, which shows good flow properties of the powdered blend.

Drug Content of Solid SEDDS

The drug content of solid SEDDS was carried out. The % assay of the solid SEDDS was found to be 98.31%.

Drug entrapment efficiency

The drug entrapment efficiency of solid SEDDS was carried out. The results of drug entrapment efficiency of solid SEDDS formulation was found to be 92.57%

Dissolution Studies of Darunavir Solid and Liquid SEDDS and Marketed product

The release of Darunavir from solid, liquid SEDDS formulations, and marketed product was determined. The concentrations were assayed spectrophotometrically at 262nm. Comparative dissolution profiles of solid and liquid SEDDS formulation (F4) with marketed product are summarized in Table 7. Solid and liquid SEDDS have shown better release profiles when compared with the pure drug and the marketed product.

Table7: Comparative results of drug release from SEDDS, Solid SEDDS and Marketed product.

Time (mins)	Dissolution media - Phosphate buffer pH 6.8 (% Drug release)		
	Marketed Product	Liquid SEDDS (F6)	Solid SEDDS
0	0	0	0
2	28.19	39.53	59.83
5	46.23	78.10	67.48
10	57.90	85.68	79.46
15	64.32	90.50	83.02
20	69.33	92.61	90.00
25	73.82	95.28	94.65
30	77.21	96.33	97.57
45	81.43	96.33	97.61
60	87.69	95.34	97.89

Fig.6: Comparative results of drug release from SMEDDS, Solid SMEDDS and Marketed product.

Particle Size Analysis for SEDDS

Droplet size of Darunavir emulsion decreased with reducing the oil content in SEDDS (Figure 7). The smaller the droplet size, the larger the interfacial surface area will be provided for drug absorption. The size of F4 was found to be below range of 71.1 nm which indicated that formulation F6 was SEDDS. The Polydispersity index of the optimized Darunavir formulation (F4) was found to be 0.064.

Figure 7: Particle size analysis of optimized formulation.

Zeta Potential

The optimized formulation F4 was shown very low polydispersive index and low viscosity. The zeta potential of the optimized Darunavir formulation was found to be very low i.e., -40.6mV. Hence, the formulation rapidly formed emulsion and remained stable for longer time (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Zeta potential of the optimized formulation.

Drug Excipient Compatibility Studies

FTIR Studies

The FTIR spectra of pure Darunavir displayed bands at 3419.9 cm^{-1} due to N-H stretch, at 2962.76 cm^{-1} due to C=N stretching, at 1732.13 cm^{-1} due to Carboxylate stretching. The spectra also showed bands at 1631.83 cm^{-1} due to C=O bending at 1107.18 cm^{-1} due to C-N bonding (Figure 9). The FTIR spectrum of Darunavir SEDDS exhibited characteristic bands consistent with the molecular structure of Darunavir which indicated that no chemical interaction occurred between the drug and excipients used in the formulation (Figure 10).

Figure 9: FTIR Spectrum of Darunavir pure drug.

Figure 10: FTIR Spectrum of optimized formulation of Darunavir liquid SEDDS.

Drug Excipient Interactions by DSC Studies

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) was performed on pure drug, excipients and optimized formulation. DSC results revealed that the pure drug Darunavir showed a melting point at 116°C, and optimized SEDDS formulation at 119 °C. There was no considerable change observed in melting endotherm of drug in optimized formulation. It indicates that there was no interaction between drug and other excipients used in the formulation (Figure 10).

Figure 11: DSC thermograms of pure drug and optimized SEDDS (F4) formulation.

Scanning electron microscopy

Micrographs of Solid SEDDS shows Liquid SEDDS adsorbed onto the surface of Neusilin US2 particles. Since the formulation process involved facilitating adsorption through physical mixing, partially covered Neusilin US2 is also visible in the field of vision. Crystalline structures characteristic of Darunavir are not seen in solid SEDDS micrographs suggesting that the drug is present in a completely dissolved state in the Solid SEDDS. Figure 12 (i) & (ii) represents the morphology of solid SEDDS. This indicates that solid SEDDS appeared as spherical particles having an even and a smooth surface.

Figure 12 (i) & (ii): Scanning Electron Microscopy of Solid SEDDS.

Bioavailability studies

Table 8: Comparison of pharmacokinetic parameters of Darunavir solid SMEDDS formulation and pure drug at different time intervals (Mean \pm SD, n = 6).

Pharmacokinetic Parameters	Darunavir solid SMEDDS	Darunavir pure drug
C _{max} (ng/ml)	121.4 \pm 3.23	137 \pm 1.23
AUC _{0-t} (ng.hr/ml)	1533.62 \pm 4.56	1638.54 \pm 4.43
AUC _{0-inf} (nng.hr/ml)	1724.45 \pm 4.76	1839.05 \pm 5.76
T _{max} (h)	2.50 \pm 0.12	3.00 \pm 0.22
t _{1/2} (h)	5.00 \pm 0.15	5.30 \pm 0.15

Figure 13: Plasma Concentrations of Darunavir solid SMEDDS formulation and pure drug at different time intervals. (Mean \pm SD, n = 6).

Pharmacokinetic parameters comparison for pure drug suspension and solid SMEDDS

Figure shows the plasma concentration–time curve in Wistar rats after a single oral dose of Darunavir solid SMEDDS formulation as compared to Darunavir pure suspension. At all the indicated time points, the Darunavir plasma concentrations in rats treated with solid SMEDDS formulation was significantly higher than those treated with pure drug. Pharmacokinetic parameters of Darunavir after oral administration of the two formulations in Wistar rats are shown in Table 8. As can be seen from the above table, the solid SMEDDS shows the increased AUC values of about $1533.62 \pm 4.56 \text{ ng.hr/ml}$ and $1638.54 \pm 4.43 \text{ ng.hr/ml}$ when compared with pure drug. C_{max} of the solid SMEDDS $121.4 \pm 3.23 \text{ ng/ml}$ was significant ($p < 0.05$) as compared to the pure drug suspension formulation $137 \pm 1.23 \text{ ng/ml}$. T_{max} of both solid SMEDDS formulation and pure drug suspension was 3.00 ± 0.22 and $2.50 \pm 0.12 \text{ h}$, respectively. AUC is an important parameter in evaluating bioavailability of drug from dosage form, as it represents the total integrated area under the blood concentration time profile and represents the total amount of drug reaching the systemic circulation after oral administration. $AUC_{0-\infty}$ infinity for solid SMEDDS formulation was higher ($1724.45 \pm 4.76 \text{ ng.hr/ml}$) than the pure drug suspension formulation $1839.05 \pm 5.76 \text{ ng.hr/ml}$. Statistically, AUC_{0-t} of the solid SMEDDS formulation was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) as compared to pure drug suspension formulation. Higher amount of drug concentration in blood indicated better systemic absorption of Darunavir from solid SMEDDS formulation as compared to the pure drug suspension formulation. Figure 13 and Figure showed the difference of HPLC chromatograms between pure drug suspension and solid SMEDDS formulations of Darunavir at maximum concentrations. Calculated concentration was found to be more for solid SMEDDS formulations compared with pure drug of Darunavir.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Systematic efforts were made to prepare nine formulations of Darunavir SEDDS by using different polymers like Capmul MCM, Castor oil, Capryol -90, Vitamin E TPGS, Kolliphor HS 15, Kolliphor RH 40, Kolliphor ELP, Gelucire 44/14, Kolliphor EL Labrasol, Lauroglycol, PEG 400, PEG 600, Propylene glycol. From this study it was concluded that, prepared liquid SEDDS was thermodynamically stable with good self emulsification efficiency and having globule size in nanometric range which may be physiologically stable. On the basis of different evaluation parameters F4 was found to be optimized formulatin. Study also concluded that, S-SEDDS of Darunavir prepared with optimized SEDDS (F4) using adsorbing agent Neusilin US2 by adsorption technique have good flow property and drug content. SSEDDS formed clear micro emulsion with micrometric size. Results of SEM demonstrate that spherical S-SEDDS can be obtained without agglomeration. In-vitro drug release of S-SEDDS was much higher than that of pure Darunavir, SEDDS and marketed formulation. Hence it was concluded that S-SEDDS can be efficiently formulated by adsorption technique using Neusilin US2 as solid carrier to enhance dissolution rate of poorly soluble drug such as Darunavir. The oral bioavailability study of Darunavir solid SMEDDS showed improvement by a factor of 1.6 compared to the suspension in rats. Thus solid SMEDDS may be used for improvement of oral bioavailability of drugs with poor water solubility and low oral bioavailability.

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